

BEGINNING AND CAUSES OF THE BALKAN CRISIS IN THE 20TH CENTURY

Jamiyla Bazarbaeva Kumatbay kizi

Master's degree of National University of Uzbekistan

Annotation: This article analyzes the beginning and causes of the Balkan crisis. The Balkan crisis had long-term consequences for the region and the whole of Europe. The Balkan crisis also led to increased international relations and diplomatic activity.

Key words: Balkan crisis, Balkan Peninsula, strategic geopolitical importance, multi-ethnic region, multi-religious region, the political and geopolitical environment, ultimatum, the First World War, international intervention.

The Balkan crisis, which occurred at the beginning of the 20th century, was caused by a number of complex and interconnected reasons. The Balkan Peninsula was a multi-ethnic and multi-religious region, where different ethnic groups and nationalities lived next to each other. National and ethnic tensions between different groups such as Serbs, Croats, Bulgarians and Albanians were deep and long-lasting. These tensions became the basis for conflicts and confrontations.

At the beginning of the 20th century, many European powers had imperial ambitions and sought to expand their power and influence in the Balkans. Austria-Hungary and the Russian Empire were especially active in this regard. Their competition for influence in the region led to tension and conflict.

The Balkan Peninsula has been the site of many territorial disputes between various states and peoples. For example, Serbia and Bulgaria disputed ownership of Macedonia, and Austria-Hungary and Russia had differences over Bosnia and Herzegovina. These disputes have become a source of conflict and tension.

The Balkan Peninsula was of strategic geopolitical importance for many European powers. It was an important crossroads for trade routes and had access to the sea. Control over this region made it possible to strengthen their power and influence in Europe. This attracted the attention and interest of various powers, which contributed to the emergence of conflicts.

All these reasons interacted and reinforced each other, which led to the emergence of the Balkan crisis and subsequent conflicts on the peninsula.

In 1912, Serbia, Bulgaria, Greece and Montenegro formed an alliance to free the Balkan Peninsula from Ottoman influence. In October 1912, the Allies began war

against the Ottoman Empire. As a result of this war, the Allies were able to liberate most of the Balkan Peninsula from Turkish rule.

However, after the victory over the Ottoman Empire, disagreements arose between the allies regarding the division of the conquered territories. This led to conflict between Bulgaria and its former allies, which ultimately led to the Second Balkan Crisis. The Second Balkan Crisis began in June 1913, when Bulgaria attacked its former allies Serbia and Greece. The war lasted about a month and ended with the defeat of Bulgaria. As a result of this conflict, the Bucharest Peace Treaty was signed, which settled the borders between the countries and stopped hostilities.

The Balkan crisis had long-term consequences for the region and the whole of Europe. It became a precursor to the First World War, as it created tension and increased competition between European powers. The crisis also led to changes in the borders and political structure of the region, which influenced future conflicts and tensions in the Balkans.

Overall, the Balkan crisis was a complex and multifaceted event that had far-reaching consequences for the region and the whole of Europe. He showed how international conflicts and contradictions can lead to serious consequences and changes in the political and geopolitical environment.

The Balkan crisis attracted the attention of many international powers and organizations who tried to intervene in the conflict or prevent its escalation. Here are some of the key participants and their reactions to the events:

Austria-Hungary was interested in supporting Serbia in order to weaken Russian influence in the Balkans. However, after the assassination of Archduke Franz Ferdinand in Sarajevo, Austria-Hungary issued a series of ultimatums to Serbia, demanding an investigation and punishment of those responsible. When Serbia did not agree to all the demands, Austria-Hungary declared war.

Russia was an ally of Serbia and sought to support it in the conflict with Austria-Hungary. Russia mobilized its troops and prepared for military intervention to defend Serbia. However, due to the difficult political situation and fears of a possible war with Austria-Hungary, Russia did not enter into a direct military conflict.

The Balkan crisis led to significant territorial changes in the Balkans. The main changes affected the Ottoman Empire, which lost most of its possessions in the Balkans. As a result of the war, Serbia, Bulgaria, Greece and Montenegro gained independence and significant territorial gains. Albania was also created as an independent state. The Balkan crisis strengthened nationalist sentiments in the Balkans. National groups, seeking independence and increasing their territories,

actively opposed the Ottoman Empire. This led to increased nationalist movements and conflicts between different ethnic groups.

The Balkan crisis became one of the reasons for the intensification of geopolitical struggle between the powers. Britain, Germany, Russia and other countries sought to strengthen their influence in the Balkans and use the conflict to their advantage. This led to further tensions and conflicts between the powers, eventually leading to the First World War.

The Balkan crisis also led to increased international relations and diplomatic activity. Various powers and organizations have made attempts to end the conflict and find a peaceful solution. However, these efforts were ineffective and the conflict continued, eventually leading to further tensions and the First World War. The Balkan crisis had a significant impact on future conflicts in the Balkans. It became a harbinger of the First World War and subsequent conflicts in the region. Nationalist and ethnic contradictions that emerged during the Balkan crisis continued to exist and subsequently led to new conflicts and wars.

In conclusion, the Balkan crisis was a complex and multifaceted conflict that occurred at the beginning of the 20th century on the Balkan Peninsula. It was caused by various factors, including the national and territorial claims of various peoples, the geopolitical interests of the great powers, and the complex relationships between different ethnic groups. The crisis led to a series of armed conflicts and changes in borders in the region. International intervention and participation also had a significant impact on developments. The effects of the Balkan Crisis are felt to this day, and it remains an important historical event that helped define the modern political map of the Balkan Peninsula.

References:

1. Ackenmann A. Preventive action in Macedonia//Peace Magazine/ May-June 1998/ P-26.
2. Annan K. Challenges of the New Peacekeeping//Peacemaking and peacekeeping for the New Century/ N.Y. P. 185.
3. Boutros-Ghali B/ Unvaquished,the United States-United Nations saga/ N.Y. 1999
4. Goulding M. Peacemonger. Balcan crisis, 2003. P.37
5. Nambiar S. UN Peacekeeping Operations in the Former Yugoslavia. N.Y. 2001/ P. 171